

ART. XXIII.—*Two Chinese-Buddhist Inscriptions found at Buddha Gayâ.* By the Rev. S. BEAL.

THESE inscriptions were found among the rubbish surrounding the Great Temple at Buddha-Gayâ; this rubbish had accumulated during the progress of the alterations and improvements carried out by the Burmese deputation who visited the Temple in 1877. Quoting from p. 65 of Dr. Rajendralâla Mitra's work on Buddha Gayâ we learn "that certain Burmese gentlemen, deputed by his Majesty the King of Burmah, arrived at Buddha Gayâ at the beginning of 1877, and with the sanction of the Mahant, who is the present owner of the Great Temple and the surrounding ground, carried on demolitions and excavations round the temple, which in a manner swept away most of the old land-marks. The remains of the vaulted gateway in front of the temple had been completely demolished and the place cleared out and levelled. The stone pavilion over the Buddhapad had been dismantled and its materials cast aside on a rubbish mound at a distance. The granite plinth beside it had been removed. The sites of the chambers brought to light by Major Mead had been cleared out. The drain-pipe and gargoye which marked the level of the granite pavement had been destroyed. The foundations of the old buildings noticed by Hiouen Tshang around the Great Temple had been excavated for bricks and filled up with rubbish. The revetment wall round the sacred Bodhi tree had been rebuilt on a different foundation on the West. The plaster ornaments on the interior facing of the sanctuary had been knocked off and covered with a coat of plain stucco, and an area of 250 feet by 230 feet levelled and surrounded by a new wall. It is much to be regretted that the attention of the authorities was not drawn to the subject when the Burmese gentlemen first came to the place, and no means

were devised to control and regulate their action. Had this been done, advantage might have been taken of their excavations to trace and identify most of those temples, topes and other structures mentioned in Buddhist writings and in the travels of the Chinese Pilgrim, and thereby to throw much new light on the history of Buddhism and Buddha. The opportunity has now been lost. The Burmese gentlemen were, doubtless, very pious and enthusiastic in the cause of their religion, but they were working on no traditional or systematic plan. They were ignorant of the true history of their faith, and perfectly innocent of all knowledge of architecture and the requirements of archæology and history, and the mischief they have done by their misdirected zeal has been serious."

So far, according to this writer, with respect to the Burmese mission to Buddha Gayâ. We should recollect, however, and be grateful whilst recollecting, that as the Great Temple at Gayâ was founded by a King of Ceylon for the entertainment of Southern Buddhist priests, so the Southern Buddhists of Burmah have, from time to time, paid attention to the preservation of the building, and it is to them, probably, we owe the existence of the temple as it is. If the Northern Buddhists had done as much for Nâlanda—and it was for their convenience this monastery was founded—we should not now have to regret the destruction and almost entire disappearance of this once famous establishment.

But anyhow the occasion of these demolitions or restorations was not allowed to pass by wholly unimproved. General Cunningham accordingly, in the summer of 1880, began a search among the rubbish surrounding the Great Temple, and it was under some twelve feet of this, that the Chinese inscriptions which are here given (or the longer of the two, for I have no exact information as to the earlier and shorter one) were found.

The first and shorter rubbing gives us the name of Chi-I, a priest of the Great Han country, presumably the writer of it. It states that Chi-I, having first vowed to exhort or encourage thirty thousand men to prepare themselves by

their conduct for a birth in heaven, also to distribute in charity thirty thousand books relating to a heavenly birth, and himself to recite as many books, then, in company with others, set out to travel through India, and arrived at Magadha, where he gazed upon the Diamond Throne, and other sacred vestiges of his religion; after this, in company with some other priests, he further vowed to continue his travels through India, apparently for the same purpose. Amongst the priests referred to, there are three named, the first Kwei Tsêih, the second Chi-I, the third Kwang Fung.

Beyond this I am unable to find anything important in the inscription. The forms of the characters may possibly be as ancient as the Han dynasty. But as the inscription has nothing to do with the figures of the seven mortal Buddhas, and the Bodhisatwa Maitreya sculptured above it, it is possible that the figures may have been executed after the inscription was placed *in situ*, and possibly much of the inscription itself erased.

There is barely a doubt whether the Great Han country refers to China. There is a record noticed by Klaproth in his *Annales des Empereurs du Japon* (p. 6, n.) concerning a country called Ta Han, somewhere to the eastward of China. As Klaproth gives no Chinese symbols, we cannot say whether the country so named is the same as that in the inscription. But if it is so, there is just a doubt whether these missionary priests were not Coreans or belonging to the Ta-han country of Klaproth.

The vow to convert the world was not an unusual one with Buddhist priests. Many of the missionaries who came to China from India were prompted to do so by this desire for the conversion of men; and we may understand that the same desire urged many Chinese priests to visit the parts of their own country bordering on India, whence they might easily advance into India itself. This might have been the case with Chi-I and his companions. If the inscription belong to the time of the Han dynasty in China, it must claim an antiquity of not later than the end of the second century A.D.

The second inscription dates from the *Tien-hi* year of the

reign of Chên Tsung of the Sung dynasty, *i.e.* 1022 A.D., and is to the effect that a priest, Ho-Yun, went to Buddha Gayâ with a view to worship the sacred relics of the place. While there, he carved a stone pagoda, with a surmounting pinnacle and a square base, thirty paces to the north of the Bodhi Tree, in honour of the thousand Buddhas. He would have also inscribed an entire *Sûtra* if his funds had been sufficient, but in place of that he left behind him the record before us, which is a hymn in praise of the three bodies of Buddha and the three thrones they occupy.

The three bodies, according to the inscription, are, the FA-SHIN (*Nirmânakâya*), the Po-SHIN (*Sâmbhôgakâya*), and the FAH-SHIN (*Dharmakâya*). In relation to the first, which represents the human body, it is described as compassionate, ready and able to deliver men from the midst of the fire. The second is the body which has appeared in various forms through countless ages, ever aiming to prepare itself for the final manifestation as Buddha, when its aim would be accomplished. The third body, or the *Dharmakâya*, is said to be: "Co-extensive with the universe, inhabiting all time, with excellences as innumerable as the sands or grains of dust, beyond all human character and transcending all human language."

The three seats or thrones are, first, that at Gayâ, which is the centre of the earth, springing from the depth of the golden circle, on which all the Buddhas have overcome the armies of Mâra with their lion voice.

The second is co-extensive with the three worlds, reaching above the heavens, renewed even after the destruction of the world.

The third is without beginning or end, unaffected by time or circumstance, imperishable as the body (of the Law) itself.

The inscription continues in the same laudatory terms, and ends with the statement that in the year above named, *viz.* A.D. 1022, two men, called I-tsing and I-lin, were sent from the Eastern capital with a *Kashâya* garment in a golden case, which they hung above the Bodhi Tree, and

which fact is recorded as supplementary to the hymn of praise of Ho-Yun.

With respect to this inscription, which has little historical value, I may simply remark that the altars or thrones at Sanchi seem to represent the first described, whilst those at Amaravati seem to point to the second, "co-extensive with the three worlds."

I will now add a restoration of the inscriptions, for which I am indebted to Mr. Douglas, of the British Museum, who procured it through the Chinese Embassy. I fear the characters have been mistaken in many cases in these transcriptions. I have only ventured, however, to change them in one or two cases, leaving a more complete restoration for scholars in China who may take an interest in the subject.

The discovery of these inscriptions has led to the supposition that they are in some way connected with Fa-hien or Hiouen Tshang. It will be well to remember therefore that many Chinese pilgrims besides these two visited India during the early centuries of our era.

For instance, we have the record of I-tsing, contained in his work *Nan-hae-k'i-kwei-niu-jä-ch'uen*, of fifty-six priests who visited India from China and neighbouring countries during the middle and end of the seventh century A.D. As some of these records are of interest, I will briefly allude to them.

With respect to I-tsing himself, or, as he was called in full, Shih-i-tsing (the symbol Shih (Śākya) is a contraction for Shih-tseu, *i.e.* a Śākya-putra, or disciple of Śākya), we read in a work *Ku-kin-shi-king-t'u-ki*, that he was a man of Ts'i-chau (in Shantung). His family name was Chang, his private name was Wen. He became a disciple when very young, and at fifteen years of age resolved to visit the western world, like the unpretending Fa-hien or the famous Hiouen Tshang; and so, in the second year of *Hien Hêng* (A.D. 671-2), he came with thirty-seven others to Kwang-fu (Canton), and of these, ten set out with him on his travels, but these all got away from the ship and left him

CHINESE INSCRIPTION FOUND AT
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W. Griggs, Photo-lith. London.

時殄魔軍力安然師子鳴讚報身座曰座高三界外色頂上

天居劫火終雍刻世工豈易摸花王各異遠妙覓道堪都寶間塵

沙數長生遍太靈讚法身座曰無始無生滅蹤橫絕去來凝

然含五趣寐靜納災般若偈潛演勞悲障密摧雖經百万劫杳杳

離塵埃我將有相之荒詞用讚無生之妙理似持蚊睫揆度穹隆

豈知高下微表歸仰之懷今將讚誦三身抄善兼及刻鑄千聖殊

勲並用奉福我本國明王遐資聖壽大宋皇帝伏願命等天

池之水滔滔而無滅無增福如神嶽之山岌岌而唯高唯峻我王

更願此地當來位繼曩法之位他方後世名標月蓋之名有讚誦

異跡靈蹤脩錄口記時大宋天禧年歲次壬戌乙巳月標記之

耳同扎佛鄉僧東京右街典教禪院義清義璘二人

同持金襴袈裟一條於摩河菩提佛塵上被掛已訖寄標於此力

古記之

懷法神各見禮書

按宋真宗天禧五

年歲次辛酉明年

壬戌改元乾興是

刻猶作天禧殆遠

別帝鄉不知改元

故耳

重建上有脫文

大漢國僧志義支發願勸三十万人修上生行施三十万卷上生

經自誦三十万卷如口德迴迴普陀今至摩竭国聖金口口過唯

口口口歸寶与諸大德等同發願往普陀口口三万人中歸寶為弟

一人志義弟二廣峰弟三下依口口弟惠品重建金口綠真義暹

口口智永奉口清蘊口並願奉口口慈尊今結良緣口口口口

按宋史載有沙門
洪蘊潭州長沙人
真宋在蜀邸時嘗
以葯方謁見

大宋國傳經講論西河僧可蘊述讚佛身座記可蘊遠別帝鄉來
瞻佛境既覩異跡靈蹤寧無福善欽讚者乎可蘊遂竭餘資於道
樹北三十餘步刻鑄千佛石塔一口所選標之會安足之方財嚴
不足以寫心法施剎恭而傾腹聊申荒句以讚無生讚覓座真容

日大雄口氏悲物留真雖無空法然有靈神群邪啓仰動識咸
親口千年久月面長新 又讚曰 四八觀無盡威顏衆好鮮頂

山盤碧玉目海透青蓮万字勾金聚雙眉毫雲纏奇哉神異手口
體絕塵烟因口影體脩讚真身佛身有三一一具讚讚化身曰

悲深月面真曾救火中人爲子留醫法繫珠作支親三車開覓路
五教拂迷塵懊惱沈淪日不逢物外身 讚報身曰 万行僧祇

滿凡出愛關根塵周淨穢相好納江山佛佛身無礙心 境絕攀
超 永拋三有海自利體閑閑 讚法身曰 覓原周法界妙好遍沙

塵湛湛無生滅冥冥絕果因居凡時不俗在聖處非真我讚心言
竭始逢清淨身三身既讚座亦頌揚讚化身座曰 五天有異跡

六合內中生深透金輪底高昇地面平塵勞終不雜水火豈能更
時殄魔軍力安然師子鳴 讚報身座曰 座高三界外色頂上

天居劫火終雍刻世工豈易摸花王各異遠妙覓道堪都寶間塵
沙數長生遍太靈 讚法身座曰 無始無生滅蹤橫絕去來凝

然含五趣寐靜納 災 般若偈潛演勞悲障密摧雖經百万劫杳杳
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豈知高下微表歸仰之懷今將讚誦三身抄善兼及刻鑄千聖殊
勳並用奉福我本國 明王遐資聖壽大宋 皇帝伏願命等天

儀法神各見禮書
按宋真宗天禧五

年歲次辛酉月年
也之水皆爲而無滅無會福神缺之山長長而行能寫能變

年歲次辛酉月年

也之水皆爲而無滅無會福神缺之山長長而行能寫能變

alone. And so with earnest resolve and unattended he went on, and after many dangers and delays came to the borders of India. He studied the languages of all the countries he passed through. Deeply he revered the sacred spots on the Vulture Peak, and the Cock-foot Mount; gladly he advanced to the Jetavana and the Deer Park, and then, taking a circuit, rested in the Nālanda College and worshipped at the Bo Tree. He studied under eminent masters, both the Little and Great Vehicle. After visiting more than thirty countries, he returned homewards, having been away some twenty years, and arriving at the river Loh (in Honan, a tributary of the Yellow River), [he disembarked]. He brought home with him nearly four hundred distinct volumes of original copies of the Sūtra, Vinaya and Abidharma (scriptures), comprising 500,000 verses. He also brought one picture of the Diamond Throne and three hundred fragments of *sarīras* (body-relics). The Heavenly Queen (*Tin-hau* or *Wu-hau*, the empress), in her reverence for religion (the law), accompanied by her family and friends, went forth from the eastern gate to meet him and his sacred treasure. His dark-clad companions bore flags; music was heard on every side as he advanced to the Shan-ki Temple. Here he rested and began his work of translation. During the years 700-703 A.D. he translated, first with (a priest) of Khoten, and afterwards by himself, in the Fuh-sien Temple of the Eastern capital, or in the Sai-ming Temple of the Western capital, twenty volumes. Afterwards, in the first year of the *Shên Lung* cycle (705), he translated in the inner precinct of the Eastern capital the following work in three chapters, "The Chant of the Peacock-rāja" (*Mayūra rāja dhāranī*), and in the Ta-fuh-sien Temple three other works.

Altogether, from the first year of the cycle *Kin-she* (under the rule of the Empress *Wu*) till the second year of the cycle *King Yün* (under the rule of the Emperor Jui Tsung) [700 A.D. to 712 A.D.], he (with others co-operating) translated fifty-six distinct treatises (*P'o*), including altogether 230 chapters (*kiouen*).

I-tsing in his narrative speaks of two routes to India from China, commonly adopted in his time; one by the Southern Seas, *i.e.* from Canton to Condore (*Kun-lun*) and thence to the straits of Malacca, Quedah, Pegu and Tamralipti: the other by the old route through the Sandy deserts to Khoten and North India, or through Tibet and Nepal to Cashmere. Confining my remarks for the present to the Southern route, I find I-tsing (*Kiouen* I. p. 7 *op. cit.*) referring to two priests of Corea, their names unknown, who starting from *Chang'an* and taking ship along the coast proceeded to the Southern Sea. Having arrived at *Shi-li-fo-shai* (Sribhōja), they proceeded westward to the coast of *Po-lu-se* and there died. We know with some certainty that the country of *Po-lu-se* is Sumatra.¹ We may therefore place *fo-shai* (Sribhōja) to the eastward of Sumatra.

I-TSING² next refers to a priest of *Yih-chau*³ named HUI-NING. He left China by sea for the south in the year 665 A.D., and passed three years in the country called *Ho-ling*.

The next notice is to the life of a priest called WAN-KI of Kiau-chau (in Chili?), who spent ten years in the Southern Sea and was very learned in the language of *Kun-lun* (Condore) and partly acquainted with Sanskrit. He afterwards retired to a lay life and resided at *Shi-lo-fo-shi* (Sribhōja).

Another priest called MOCIA-DEVA, a Cochin Chinese, went to India by the Southern Sea route, and having visited all the countries of that part, arrived at the Mahâbodhi Temple, where he adored the sacred relics and died æt. 24.

KWEI-CHUNG, another priest of Cochin China, went by the Southern Sea to Ceylon, afterwards in company with a priest called HÜN-CHIN he proceeded to the Bodhi Tree, and afterwards to Râjagṛiha, and being taken sick in the Bamboo garden (Veluvana) he died there aged thirty years.

We next read of a priest of the Mahâyana school called TANG or "the lamp" (*dîpa*), who went with his parents when

¹ Compare Bretschneider, "The Knowledge possessed by the Ancient Chinese of the Arabs," etc. p. 16n.

² K.T. p. 11. 1.

³ Yih Chau in Chili.

young to the land of *Drárapati* (Sandoway in Burmah) and there became a priest. He returned with the Chinese envoy to the capital. Afterwards he went by the Southern Sea route to Ceylon, where he worshipped the tooth; and then proceeding through South India and crossing into Eastern India, arrived at *Tamralipti*: being attacked by robbers at the mouth of the river, he barely escaped with his life; he resided at Tamralipti for twelve years, having perfected himself in Sanskrit, he then proceeded to Nálanda and Buddha Gayâ, then to Vesâli and the Kusi country, and finally died at Kusinagara, in the Pari Nirvâna Temple.

We next read of two priests of Kao-tchaing (Turfan) going in company with a Chinese envoy through the southern seas. They died, however, on board ship. Their books (the *Yoga Śâstra* and others) I-TSING remarks are still at SHI-LI-FOU-SHAI.

I-TSING at the beginning of the second part of his treatise alludes to a priest called TAO-LIN of King-chau (in Hupeh) whose Sanskrit name was SILAPRABHA, who embarked in a foreign ship and passing through the copper-pillars stretched away to LANKA (Kamalanká), and then, keeping along the Kalinga coast (*i.e.* the coast of Pegu), they came to the country of the naked men. The king of this country behaved well to the pilgrim and he remained there several years. He then proceeded to Tamralipti, where he passed three years learning the Sanskrit language. After visiting the Vajrâsana and worshipping the Bodhi Tree, he passed to NÁLANDA, where he studied the *Kosha*, and after a year or two went to the Vulture peak, near Râjagriha, and finally proceeded to South India; and going through the Marâthâ country in Western India he studied a work called the *Ta-mung-chan*, in Sanskrit the *Vedi dhâva piṭaka*. The current tradition is that this work was in 100,000 ślokas, which, in a Chinese translation, would represent 300 chapters (*kiouem*), but that a great portion is lost—and that, after the death of the great Holy One, the spirit of the verses was preserved by ARYA NĀGĀRJUNA.

TAO-LIN after this proceeded to Kaśmir and the country of

UDYĀNA, and dwelt in KAPISA, where he adored the skull-bone of Buddha. He then returned by sea¹ to Qučdàh (Kie-c'ha). He was here informed by some Northern Tartars (*hu*) that there were two priests in their country agreeing in description with some friends of his; he returned, therefore to North India, where he died aged fifty years or so.

Another priest called TAN-KWONG, of the same district in China, went to India by the Southern Sea route, and having arrived at A-LI-KI-LO (Arakan?), he was reported to have found much favour with the king of that country, and to have got a temple built and books and images; in the end, as was supposed, he died there.

HWUI-MING, another priest from the same district, set out to go to India by the Southern Sea route, but the ship being baffled by contrary winds put in at TUNG-CHU (copper pillars) in Ma-yuen, and after stopping at SHANG-KING returned to China.

HWUI-TA, a priest of Kung-chow, and the district of Kiang Ning, was a man of high family. He appears to have accompanied an envoy in a Persian ship to the Southern Seas. Having arrived at Fo-shai (Sribhôja) he remained there six months studying the *Sabdavidya*; the king was highly courteous, and on the occasion of his sending a present to the country of *Mo-lo-yu* (Malaya) HWUI-TA proceeded there, and remained two months. He then went on to Qučdàh, and then at the end of winter went in the royal ship towards Eastern India. Going North from Qučdàh, after ten days or so they came to the country of the naked man. For two or three *lis* along the Eastern shore there were nothing but cocoa-nut trees and forests of betel vines. The people, when they saw the ship, came alongside in little boats with the greatest clamour; there were upwards of one hundred such boats filled with cocoa-nuts and plantains; they had also baskets, etc., made of rattan; they desired to exchange these things for whatever we had

¹ The Southern Sea route.

that they fancied, but they liked nothing so much as bits of iron. A piece of this metal two fingers length in size would buy as many as five or ten cocoa-nuts. The men here are all naked, the women wear a girdle of leaves; the sailors in joke offered them clothes, but they made signs that they did not want any such articles. This country, according to report, is south-west of Sze-ch'uan. The country produces no iron, and very little gold and silver; the people live on cocoa-nuts and some esculent roots, but have very little rice or cereals. Iron is very valuable; they call it *Lu-a*. The men are not quite black, of middling height, they use poisoned arrows, one of which is fatal. Going for half a month in a north-west direction we came to Tamralipti, which is the southern district of East India. This place is some sixty stages or more from Nâlanda and the Bodhi Tree. Meeting the priest called "Lamp of the great vehicle" (Mahâyana dipa) in this place, they remained together there one year, learning Sanskrit and practising themselves in the *Śabda-śāstra*. They then went on with some hundred or so merchantmen towards Central India. When about ten days journey from the Mahâbodhi, in a narrow pass, the road being bad and slippery, Hwui-ta was left behind and attacked by robbers, who stripped him and left him half dead in a ditch. At sundown some villagers rescued him and gave him a garment. Going on north he came to NÂLANDA, and after visiting all the sacred spots in the neighbourhood he remained at Nâlanda ten years, and then going back to TAMRALIPTI, he returned to Qučdâh, and with all his books and translations, amounting in all to 500,000 ślokas, enough to fill 1000 vols.: he remained at Śribhōja.

SHEN-HING, a priest of Sin Chow, also went to Śribhōja, where he died.

The priest LING-WAN having gone through Annam came to India, and erected under the Bodhi Tree a figure of MÂITREYA BODHISATWA one cubit in height, and of exquisite character.

SENG-CHI, a priest and companion of the former, went to India by the Southern Sea route, and arrived at SAMOTATA.

The king of that country, named HARSHA VARDHANA, a Upāsaka, greatly revered the three objects of worship, and devoted himself to his religious duties; he had made, day by day, above 100,000 figures of Jemma; had read through the Great *Prajña*, consisting of 100,000 ślokas, and was most punctual in his acts of worship, etc.

A priest, CHI-'SZ, is mentioned who went to the South and resided at SHANG-KING, near Cochin China. He then went south to Sribhōja, and afterwards proceeded to India.

A priest, WOU KING, in company with the last, left Hainan with an easterly wind; after a month he arrived at Sribhōja. He then went in the royal ship for fifteen days to Malaya, in another fifteen days to Quēdàh, then waiting till the end of winter; going west for thirty days he arrived at NAGA-VADANA (Nagapatam?), whence after two days' sea voyage he came to Sinhapura (Ceylon). He there worshipped the sacred tooth, and then going N.E. for a month arrived at the country of O-li-ki-lo (Arakan). This is the eastern limit of East India. It is a part of the country of Champa (Siam). Staying here one year he moved towards Eastern India with his companion, CHI-'sz. This place is about 100 stages from Nālanda. After this he proceeded to the Mahabodhi Temple in the Mung country (*i.e.* the Temple of KHARDEH). Having rested here, he again returned to Nālanda and studied the *Yoga*, *Kosha*, and other works. Moved with a desire to find copies of the *Vinaya*, he again repaired to the Khardch (*kie-lo-'ha*) temple. About two stages from this he speaks of a saintly artisan who by practising the rules of the Bodhisatwa CHANNA, expected to obtain the power of entering the dim caverns of earth. In the end he died at Nālanda.

FA-SHIN also started by the southern route, and after passing Shang-king (Saigon), Ku-long, Kaling, and Quēdàh, he died.

Putting together the notices to be found in I-TSING's works we may conclude that the sea-route between China and India in the early years of the TANG dynasty was by way of Java, Sumatra, the straits of Malacca, the coast of Burma and

Arakan, to Tamralipti, or else by the more adventurous way of Ceylon from Quçdàh. It seems that the Condore Islands were a centre of trade, and that the language of the natives of these islands was used generally through the Southern Seas; at least I-TSING speaks of himself as interpreting the language at Sribhôja.

We have one or two points of some certainty in the itinerary of these pilgrims. For instance in the *Si-yu-ki* Hiouen Tshang (iii. 82) says that to the N.E. of SAMOTATA is the country called ŚRIKSHETRA, to the S.E. of this is KAMALANGKA, to the east of this is DĀRAPATI (read Dvārapati). This country has been identified by Captain St. John (*Phoenix*, May, 1872) with old Tung-oo and Sandoway in Burmah, lat. 18° 20' N. long. 94° 20' E., it is in fact the "door land" between Burma and Siam; this latter being called Champa or Lin-I. Hiouen Tshang remarks that to the S.W. of *Lin-I*, or Siam, in the country of the YAVANAS, or, as they are called in his text, the YEN-MO-NA. We do not read of this country in I-TSING; it may, probably, represent Cambodia.

I now turn to a brief consideration of the other pilgrims named by I-TSING who reached India by the northern route.

1. The Shaman YUAN-CHIU, a native of SIN-NANG in TAI-CHAU, went to India, leaving KIN-FU, crossing the desert of drifting sands, passing through the Iron gates, Tukhâra and Tibet, he arrived by degrees at Jâlandhara, where he remained four years. Being in favour with the MUNG king he studied with him the Sanskrit language and the Buddhist *Śâtras* and the *Vinaya*. Going southwards he came to the Mahâbodhi, where again he passed four years visiting the sacred relics of the Holy One and looking up with reverence to the features of Maitreya, which were carved there. He then went to Nâlanda, where he remained three years, and made the acquaintance of a priest called *Shin-kwong*. He also met here a noted priest of Ceylon, from whom he received a copy of the *Yoga* and other sacred books. Going north along the Ganges he remained in the SIN-TCHE and other temples for three years and then returned to China; passing through Nepal and Tibet, where he met his old

friend, WEN-SHING-KUNG, he arrived by way of Western Tibet and Eastern Hia. Again (664 A.D.) he returned to India through Tibet, accompanied by a Brahman he had met at Loyang, called LOKAYATA; travelling towards the Marâthâ country, he passed through Tukhâra, and in the course of a year came to the NAVA-VIHÂRA, where he saw the water-pitcher of Tathâgata and other sacred relics; he then went on to KAPISA, where he worshipped the skull-bone at NAGARAHARA, and took an impression of it to see whether he would be fortunate or no. Then passing through Sindh he came to the Ra-ta (Marâthâ) country; he here found the Mung King and remained with him four years, then travelling through South India he arrived on his return journey at the diamond seat at Gayâ, whence he went on to the Nâlanda temple, where I-TSING saw him; after further travels, finding it impossible to return by way of Nepal, and the way through Kapisa being now held by the TA-SHI, *i.e.* the Arabs,¹ he returned to the Amaravati country, where he sickened and died, æt. 60.

2. TAO HI, a Doctor of the Law, a man of the district LIH-SHING, of the department Ts'ai-chau (Shantung?), his Sanskrit name ŚRIDEVA. He was a man of noble descent. Having gone through India, visiting the sacred places, he came to the Mahâbodhi, where he remained several years, and then proceeded to Nâlanda. He likewise visited the country of Kusi (Nagara). The Mung king of the AMARAVATI country greatly respected him. Whilst remaining at Nâlanda he studiously applied himself to the Great Vehicle. He resided also in the Chu-po-pun-na (the Garden of the Cremation, the Temple of the Nirvâna), and studied the *Vinaya piṭaka* and the *Śabda vidya*. Whilst in the Ta-hsio Temple (the Mahâbodhi) he engraved a memorial tablet in the Chinese language. He left more than 400 Chinese vols., *Sûtras* and *Śâstras*, at Nâlanda. I-TSING did not meet him

¹ In Bretschneider (*Arabs*, etc.), p. 8, we read that the King of the Ta-shi, by name *Han-mi-mo-mo-ni*, in the year 651 sent for the first time an envoy with presents to the Chinese court, and at the same time announced in a letter that the house Ta-shi had reigned 34 years and had had three kings.

(he fell sick in the Amaravati country, and died, aged fifty years or so), but he saw his chamber.

3. SSE-PIN, Doctor of the Law, a man of Ts'AI-CHAU, went after HUAN-CHIN through North India, and then through Western India, till he came to AMÂRAKŪVA. He there dwelt in the Royal Temple, in high favour with the King. Here he met TAOU-HI, a fellow townsman. After remaining here one summer, he sickened and died, æt. thirty-five years.

4. ARYAVARMA, a Corean, in the middle period *Chêng-kwan*, 638 A.D., left Chang'an and came to Nâlanda, where he engaged himself in copying many *Sûtras*, and was deeply versed in the *Vinaya* and *Abhidharma*. After going eastward and visiting the Cock-foot Mountain, and bathing in the Dragon-pool to the westward, he died at Nâlanda, æt. about seventy.

5. HWUI-NIEH, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, in the middle of the *Chi-kwan* period, 638 A.D., went to the West and dwelt in the Bodhi Temple, where he adored the sacred relics, and then went to Nâlanda, where he dwelt for a long time, reading and studying. I-TSING, when arranging some Chinese books, suddenly saw under the title this record: "Whilst dwelling under the Tooth-brush Tree, the Corean priest HWUI-NIEH wrote this record." On inquiry at the Temple, the priests said that he died there the same year, about sixty years of age. The Sanskrit books he wrote were preserved at Nâlanda.

6. YUAN TA'I, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, called by the Sanskrit name of Sarvajnanadeva. In the year *Yung-hwei* (650 A.D.) he went by the Tibetan road through Nepal to Mid-India; he there worshipped the relics at the Bodhi Tree. Afterwards, going to the Tukhâra country, he met TAOU-HI, with whom he returned to the Ta-hsio Temple, Mahâbodhi. Afterwards he returned to China, and was not heard of again.

7. YUAN-HAU, a Doctor of the Law, a Corean, went with YUAN-CHIN, in the middle of the *Chêng-kwan* period, to India, and reaching the Ta-hsio Temple, he died there.

8. BODHDHARMA, a man of the Tukhâra country, of great

bodily size and strength, came to China, and became a priest. He wandered through the nine provinces begging as a religious mendicant. Afterwards going to India to adore the sacred vestiges, I-TSING met him at Nâlanda; afterwards he went to North India and died when fifty years old or so.

9. TAOU-LIH, a Doctor of the Law, of Ping-chau, went by way of the Sandy desert and the Tsih rock to Nepal, and afterwards came to the Ta-hsio Temple, where he remained several years; he then returned to Nepal, where he still is.

10. TAOU-SING, a Doctor of the Law, of Ping-chau, called in Sanskrit CHANDRADEVA, in the last year of the *Chêng-kwan* period (649 A.D.), went by the Tu-fan road to Mid India; he arrived at the Bodhi Temple where he worshipped the Chaityas; afterwards going to Nâlanda, he was there much honoured by the king on account of his youth. After that, going twelve stages to the eastward, he came to the King's Temple, where they study only the Little Vehicle. He remained here many years, learning the books of the *Tripitaka* according to the Hinayâna. Returning to China through Nepal, he died.

11. SHANG-TIH, a contemplative priest, of Ping-chau. He longed for the joys of the Western Paradise, and with the view of being born there he devoted himself to a life of purity and religion (reciting the name of Buddha). He vowed to write out the whole of the *Prajña-Sûtra*, occupying 10,000 chapters. Desiring to worship the sacred vestiges, and so by this to secure for himself the greater merit with a view to a birth in that heaven, he travelled through the nine provinces, desiring wherever he went to labour in the conversion of men, and to write the sacred books. Coming to the coast he embarked in a ship for Kalinga. Thence he proceeded by sea to the Malaya country, and thence wishing to go to Mid India he embarked in a merchant ship for that purpose. Being taken in a storm the ship began to founder, and the sailors and merchants were all struggling with one another to get aboard a little boat that was near. The captain of the ship being a believer and anxious to save the priest called out to him with a loud voice to come aboard

the boat, but SHANG-TIH replied, "I will not come—save the other people." And so he remained silently absorbed, as if a short term of life were agreeable to one possessed of the heart of Bodhi. Having refused all help he clasped his hands in adoration, and looking towards the West he repeated the sacred name of AMITA, and when the ship went down, these were his last words. He was about 50 years of age. He had a follower unknown to me, who also perished with his master, also calling on the name of Amita Buddha.

12. MATISINHA, a man of the capital; his common name being *Wong-po*. This man accompanied the priest SSE-PIN, and arriving at the middle land dwelt in the Sin-ché Temple. Finding his progress little in the Sanskrit language, he went to Nepal, and died on the way there, æt. 40.¹

13. YUAN-HWUI, a Doctor of the Law, son of a general, according to report. Leaving North India he dwelt in Kaśmir and took charge of the Royal Elephants. The King of this country delighted day by day in going to the different Temples, the Dragon-Lake Mountain Temple, the Kung Yang Temple. This is where the 500 Rahats received charity. Here also the venerable MADYANTIKA, the disciple of ANANDA, converted the Dragon King. This priest exhorted the King of Kaśmir by a great exercise of Royal clemency to remit the punishment of more than 1000 persons who were condemned to death—the king in consequence let them go. Having remained here some years he went southwards and came to the great Bodhi Temple, where he worshipped the Bodhi Tree, beheld the Lake of "Mu-chin" (Muchhalinda) ascended the Vulture peak, etc. After this he went back to Nepal and died there.

14. Again, there was a man who accompanied the envoy by the Northern route to the Tukhâra country, and there lodged in the Nâva-vihâra. In this establishment the principles of the Little Vehicle were taught. Having become a priest he took the name of CHITAVARMA. Having received the precepts he declined to eat the three pure things, on

¹ Nepal has a poisonous medicine which kills many.

which the master of the convent said, "Tathâgata, our Great Master, permitted these five things as food, why do you object to them?" He answered, "All the Books of the Great Vehicle forbid them; this is what I formerly practised; I cannot now bring myself to change." The Superior answered, "I have established a practice here in agreement with the three sacred collections, and you follow your own interpretation, which is contrary to mine; I cannot permit this difference of opinion, I cease to be your Master." Chittavarma was thus reluctantly obliged to yield. Then having learned a little Sanskrit he returned by the Northern route. I know no more about him.

Again, there were two men who lived in Nepal, they were the children of the wet-nurse of the Duke-Prince of Tibet (Fu-fan). They both were ordained, but one went back to lay life. They lived in the Temple of the Heavenly Kings. They spoke Sanskrit well and understood Sanskrit books.

15. LUNG, a Doctor of the Law, I know not whence he came. In the *Chêng Kwan* period, 627-650 A.D., he went by the Northern route to North India, wishing to visit the sacred spots. In Mid India he got a Sanskrit copy of the *Fâ-hwa* (Lotus of the Good Law), and having gone to Gandhâra he died there.

16. NING-YUEN, a man of Yih-chau, a Doctor of the Law, whose Sanskrit name was CHINTA-DEVA. He embarked in a ship of Cochin-China, and came to the KALINGA country, and thence to Ceylon. Whilst the king was engaged in worship, this priest, concealing himself in a private chamber, tried to steal the tooth relic with a view to bring it to his own country and worship it. He had it concealed in his hand, and was taking it away, when by careless exposure of it he was detected, and driven disgracefully away. He went to South India, and it was related that he was going towards the Mahâbodhi, but then, losing all power of digestion, he died on the road where he had rested. I know not what his age was.

They now keep this tooth relic carefully guarded in a

high tower, it is locked up and sealed by five officers, and when opened great uproar (of music?) is made through the town and outskirts. It is worshipped every day with flowers and incense, when taken out it is placed on a golden flower, and its brilliancy is everywhere diffused. A tradition says that if the relic were lost then the RAKSHAS would devour (it?). There is also a tradition which says that some day it will be taken to China, but this must be by Divine interference, and not by human contrivance.

17. I-LONG, a priest of Yih-chau, well versed in the *Vinaya Pitaka*, and in the interpretation of the *Yoga*, set forth from Chang'an with a priest Chi-ngan, of his own province, and an eminent man called I-huan, and after travelling through the Southern Provinces came to NIAU-LUI, and there embarked on board a merchant ship. Having arrived at Langkia (Kamalanka?) Chi-ngan died. I-LONG, with his other companion, went on to Ceylon, where they worshipped the Tooth, and having obtained various books, returned through Western India. It is not known where he is now residing. He has not been heard of in Mid India.

18. SIN-CHIU, a Doctor of the Law, his country not known. His Sanskrit name CHARITA-VARMA. Taking the Northern route, he arrived in the Western country, and lived in the Sin-ché Temple. In an upper room of this Temple he constructed a sick chamber, and left it for ever for the use of sick brothers. He himself died here. Some days after his illness, in the middle of the night, he suddenly exclaimed: "There is Bodhisatwa, with outstretched hand, beckoning me to his lovely abode;" and then, closing his hands, with a long sigh he expired, æt. thirty-five.

19. SANGHAVARMA, a man of Samarkand, when young crossed the Sandy Desert and came to China. Afterwards, in company with the Envoy, he came to the Great Bodhi Temple and the Vajrâsana, where he burnt lamps in worship for seven days and seven nights. Moreover, in the Bodhi Hall, under the Tree of Asoka, he carved a figure of Buddha and Kwan-tseu-tsai Bodhisatwa. He then returned to China. Afterwards, being sent to KWAI-CHIAU (Cochin-China), there

was great scarcity of food there. He daily distributed food, and was so affected by the sorrows of the fatherless and bereaved orphans, that he was moved to tears as he visited them. He was on this account named the weeping Bodhisatwa. He died shortly afterwards from infection caught there, which soon terminated fatally, æt. about sixty.

20. WAN-YUN, a Doctor of the Law, of Loyang, travelling through the Southern parts of China, came to Cochinchina, thence went by ship to Kalinga, where he died.

21. HWUI-LUN, a Korean, otherwise called Prajñavarman, came from his own country to Fu-chau, and thence to Chang'an. Being sent to follow the priest YUAN-CHIU, he arrived in the Western countries and dwelt for some time (ten years) at Amarāvati, in the Sin-ché Temple.

He afterwards went through the Eastern frontiers, and came to the Temple of the Tukhâra priests. Originally this was built by the Tukhâra people for their own priests. The Temple was called Gandhârasanda. *Hwui-Lun* dwelt here, and perfected himself in Sanskrit. All priests who come from the North dwell in this Temple. To the west of the *Ta-hsio* Temple is the Temple of the Kapisa country; this is also a rich and large establishment, for the diffusion of the Little Vehicle. Priests from the North also dwell here. The Temple is called *Gunacharita*.

Two stages to the north-east of the *Ta-hsio* is a Temple called *Kiu-lu-kiä*,¹ because a king of the Southern country, called *Kiu-lu-kiä*, had long ago built it. This establishment, though poor, was very strict in its teaching. Recently a king, called *Sun-Army*,² built by the side of the old Temple another, which is now newly finished. Priests of the South coming to this part occupy this Temple.

All parts of the world have their appropriate temples, except China, so that priests from that country have many hardships to endure. Eastward, about forty stages following the course of the Ganges, we come to the Mrigasikavana Temple. Not far from this is a ruined establishment called

¹ Chalukya? *Charaka* according to *Eitel* and *Stas. Julien*.

² Adityasena (*Burgess*).

the Tchina Temple. The old tradition says that formerly a Mahârâja called Śrigupta built this for the priests of China, At this time some Chinese priests, about twenty men or so, came from Sz'chuen to the Mahâbodhi Temple to pay worship to it, on which the king, seeing their piety, gave them as a gift this plot of land. This is about 500 years ago. The land now belongs to the King of Eastern India, whose name is Devavarma.

The Mahâbodhi Temple, near the Diamond Throne, was built by a king of the SÎNHALA country some time since for the use of priests of Ceylon. Going N.E. seven stages we come to the NĀLANDA Temple; this was built by an old king, Śri ŚAKRĀDITYA, for a Bhikshu of Northern India called RĀJA BHĀJA; after beginning it, he was much obstructed by other people, but his descendants finished it and made it by far the most magnificent establishment in Jambudwipa. This building is four square, like a city. There are four large gateways of three storeys each. Each storey is some ten feet in height. The whole covered on the outside with tiles.

Outside the western gate of the Great Hall of the Temple is a large Stûpa and various Chaityas, each erected over different sacred vestiges, and adorned with every kind of precious substance.

The Superior is a very old man; the Karmadana or Vihâraswâmi or Vihârapâla is the chief officer after the Superior, and to him the utmost deference is paid.

This is the only temple in which, by Imperial order, a water-clock is kept to determine the right time. The night is divided into three watches, during the first and last of which there are religious services; in the middle watch, as the priests may desire, they can watch or repose. The method in which this clock determines the time is fully described in the "*K'hi-kwei-ch'uen*."

The temple is called ŚRI NĀLANDA VIHĀRA, after the name of the Nâga called Nanda.

The great temple opens to the west; going about twenty paces from the gate there is a stûpa about 100 feet high.

This is where the Lord of the world (Lokanâtha) kept *Wass* (the season of the rains) for three months; the Sanskrit name is Mûlagandhakoti. Northwards, 50 paces is a great stûpa even higher than the other; this was built by BALÂDITYA—very much revered—in it is a figure of Buddha turning the wheel of the law. South-west is a little chaitya about ten feet high. This commemorates the place where the Brahman, with the bird in his hand, asked questions; the Chinese expression *Su-li-fau-to* means just the same as this.¹

To the west of the Mûlagandha Hall is the tooth-brush tree of Buddha (this is not the willow-tree).

On a raised space is the ground where Buddha walked. It is about two cubits wide, fourteen or fifteen long, and two high. There are lotus flowers carved out of the stone, a foot high, fourteen or fifteen in number, to denote his steps.

Going from the temple south to RÂJAGRÎHA is thirty *li*. The Vulture Peak and the Bambu Garden are close to this city. Going S.W. to the Mahâbodhi is seven stages (*yojanas*). The same due south to the "Honoured Foot-print." To VESÂLI is twenty-five stages north. To the Deer Park twenty or so stages west. East to TAMRALIPTI is sixty or seventy stages. This is the place for embarking for China from Eastern India and close to the sea. There are about 3500 priests in the temple at NÂLANDA, which is supported by revenues derived from land (villages) given by a succession of kings to the monastery.²

So far I have followed the records of I-TSING. They show, at any rate, that India was visited by a succession of Chinese priests during the early part of the Tang dynasty. We may hope that the two inscriptions discovered at Buddha-Gayâ will not be the last to be found there (or in the neighbourhood), and that we may yet find some record relating to one or more of these devoted pilgrims.

¹ But here I-tsing is in error.

² A stage 𑖀𑖩𑖪 is equal to a *yojana*.